

EFFECT OF REAL EARNINGS MANAGEMENT ON THE MARKET VALUE OF LISTED MANUFACTURING FIRMS IN NIGERIA

***Akosile Akindele Iyiola, Akinkunmi Maruf Akinsola and Olowolaju Philip Segun**
Department of Accounting, Joseph Ayo Babalola University, Ikeji-Arakeji, Osun State, Nigeria.
Email: aiakosile@jabu.edu.ng / marufakinkunmi@student.jabu.edu.ng / olowosegun2014@gmail.com
 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17234803>

<p>Keywords: <i>Earnings Management, Market Value, Tobin Q, Real Earnings, Manufacturing Firms</i></p>	<p>Abstract: <i>The study examined the effect of real earnings management on the market value of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study population comprised fifty-one (51) listed manufacturing firms while purposive sampling method was employed to select sample size of thirty-eight (38) listed firms. Data were collected from the sampled listed manufacturing firms for the period 2011-2021. The analysis of the study was done through panel regression-random effect. The results revealed that real earnings management exerts negative influence on the market value of the sampled firms measured with Tobin Q ($t=-2.411$; $p<0.05$) respectively. The study concluded that real earnings management are detrimental to the market value of Nigerian listed manufacturing firms. The study recommended that management of Nigerian manufacturing firm should put measures in place to limit the practice of real and accrual earnings management.</i></p>
--	---

INTRODUCTION

Earnings management is a common technique in corporate businesses that has the potential to alter firm value over time. Earnings to shareholders and/or stakeholders of any organization act as the firm's faith on which the stakeholders rely on to make returns on their invested capital (Tolulope et al., 2018). As a result, it has become one of the most important accounting items in financial statements. Abata and Migiro (2016), explained earnings as a vital component in the decision-making process of dividend policy. This is because earnings act as a

guide for making investment decisions and as a valuable tool for evaluating a company's success. The reality is that controlling earnings is likely to cause organizations' performance to be unreal, negating the aim of financial statements' relevance and credibility. As a result, it is critical for accounting professionals to pay attention to earnings management because it helps to keep financial statements relevant to users, particularly in the area of decision-making. However, earnings management occurs when managers use judgment to organize transactions in such a way that they deceive stakeholders

***Akosile Akindele Iyiola, Akinkunmi Maruf Akinsola and Olowolaju Philip Segun**

about the company's underlying economic performance or influence contractual outcomes that are based on reported financial information (Nwaobia et al., 2019).

There are two recognized forms of earnings management which are the real and accrual-based earnings management (Salome et al., 2021). What differentiates the two forms is the nature of activities being manipulated. Real earnings management refers to the manipulation of a company's cash flow by management through the company's operational activities (Sun & Lan, 2014). Concerning accrual earnings management, the timing of expenses and revenue recognition is shifted from one period to another in order to meet earnings' target. The way in which this is done is either by advancing the recognition of revenue or delaying expenses recognition. The discretionary expenses include: advertising, maintenance expenses, and research and development (R&D) expenses which are decreased in order to increase profit. Thus, good and bad earnings management (Scott, 2012), efficient and opportunistic earnings management, are two perspectives on earnings management. Earnings can be forecasted, and they can become a signal for increased earnings quality (Sunardi, 2018). Efficient earnings management is shown by the firm's increasing value, including an improvement in its earnings' persistence (Gunny, 2010). Insiders, management, and the controlling shareholders are all getting richer, indicating that

opportunistic earnings management is taking place.

The inconsistent financial statement information which compromises the reality due to earnings management can harm shareholders as the decision making by shareholders will not align with the firm performance. A financial reporting prepared using accounting principle is the basis upon which the management of firm communicates with outside stakeholders on the basis of the information disclosed by the management of the firm, the stakeholders of the firm make decisions, like resource allocation (Susanto, 2017). Hence, the quality of information communicated through the financial report determines the quality of these decisions which in turn determines the future direction and destiny of the firm.

Statement of the Problem

Earnings of a firm are the most fundamental and important information which the financial reporting discloses as the firm's future is also determined by it. Earnings are usually a reflection of a company's performance. The most troubling aspect of using accrual accounting in financial statements is earnings management (Subramanyam, 2014). Management or manipulation of this earning results when the managers incorporated their personal judgement and discretion in the determination of earnings. The implications of these earnings manipulation for the firm's earnings and value are long lasting. Hence, earnings management has a crucial role in determining earnings of the

firm and its future and has been extensively discussed and researched in the corporate finance literature.

Earnings management is a method through which accountants distort financial information for decades, but it has lately acquired traction as a result of recent corporate scandals. Misappropriation of shareholder's funds, falsification of financial records, and collusion with auditors to give unqualified reports were all part of the controversies. These scandals, which led industry titans like Cadbury Plc. and Lever Brothers, now known as Unilever Nigeria Plc., to the restatement of their financial reports, have harmed the integrity of financial reporting, raising issues about the accuracy of financial statements and the information available to consumers (Uwuigbe, 2011). Real earnings management and accrued based earnings management are the two types of earnings management.

Weak corporate governance structure has provided opportunity for managers to engage in earnings management practices. There have been several corporate failures in Nigeria (Cadbury Plc., Lever Brothers, now known as Unilever Nigeria Plc., and bank failures such as Fin Bank and Spring Bank), all of which have been linked to mismanagement, as well as poor financial disclosure system (Uwuigbe, 2011). However, Remenaric et al. (2018) argued that even though earnings management can have a positive impact on a company's business in the short term, in the long run it will likely result in

decreased stock prices, insolvency, and even bankruptcy. In addition, the prevalence of earnings management may become an indictment on a law regulatory agency and environment which is prone to abuse by unscrupulous individuals (Salome et al., 2021). As a result, manipulative behaviour on the part of managers may have a significant impact on accounting performance measures such as return on asset, return on equity, and return on capital employed among others (Umoren et al., 2018). Several studies such as Abass and Ayub, 2019; Abdullahi et al., 2020; Huang et al., 2021; Liu & Tsai 2015; Okafor & Ezeagbe ,2018; Olotu et al, 2019; Sanyaolu & Job-Olatunji, 2017; Susanto, 2017; Salome, et al, 2021; Nwaobia, et al, 2019; Ubesie et al., 2020; Wilson, 2015) conducted different studies on nexus between earnings management and firm value. The above studies have reported mixed results on the impact of each of the earnings management as some reported significant relationship, while some failed to find significant impact. In addition, the studies focusing on the link between earnings management and market value in Nigeria context have largely focused on accrual earnings management, while real earnings management which firms are now shifting to is underexplored. Furthermore, the impact of earnings management on market value is yet to receive attention in literature by focusing on manufacturing firms. All these identified gaps become the vacuum to be filled in this study. This fundamental question will guide this study. What

***Akosile Akindede Iyiola, Akinkunmi Maruf Akinsola and Olowolaju Philip Segun**

is the effect of real earnings management on the market value of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria?

The main objective of the study was to examine how real earnings management influence the market value of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The outcome obtained from this study will provide investors with more information on earnings management with required information on the desirability of earnings management based on the implication of the practice on market value of the firm. Also, investors will be furnished with useful information on the need to consider earnings management practices of firms, in making their investment decisions. The study also serves as a guide to investors in making appropriate investment decisions

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Review

Earnings Management

Earnings management was first studied by Hepworth (1953) as earnings smoothening. For the first time, McNichols, (2000) and Abbas & Ayub, (2019) altered the expression earnings management for earnings smoothening. Therefore, the focus of earnings management was to prepare a summary of firm performance which enforce and reflect the intended results. Schipper (1989) defined earnings management as interference in financial reporting process which is deliberate and intended to achieve desired level of earnings. This means earnings may be increased or decreased or smoothened based on the targets and goals set by the

management (Abbas & Ayub, 2019). Earnings management can be described as any management move that impacts reported income but delivers no genuine benefit to the firm and may, in fact, be negative in the long run. However, earning management, according to Abdullah and Mohammed (2004), is the use of accounting procedures by managers to attain their own self-interest by deceiving stakeholders through the provision of skewed financial statements. Earning management can be attributed to the flexibility of choice afforded by accounting rules. Accounting principles enable firm agents (managers) to choose from a variety of reporting techniques and make assumptions based on the unique characteristics of their business environment. Earning management, on the other hand, refers to managers' efforts to change a firm's earnings by utilizing a certain technique of accounting or a replacement method, taking into account a single time worn-returning item, or other strategies that could be employed in a short period of time to affect earning (Abbas & Ayub, 2019)

The term "earnings management" refers to a situation in which the manager in charge of preparing and presenting financial statements and annual reports has access to more information than other stakeholders. This type of situation usually results in an information asymmetry problem between managers and stakeholders, which is caused by imperfect markets in which stakeholders do not have all of the correct necessary information on a timely

***Akosile Akindele Iyiola, Akinkunmi Maruf Akinsola and Olowolaju Philip Segun**

basis (Umobong & Akani, 2015; Sanyaolu & Job-Olatunji, 2017). Earning management, according to Gulzar and Wang (2011), is the manipulation of reported firms' operations by those within the firm, either to mislead those with economic interests in the firm or to achieve other goals.

Real Earnings Management

Schipper (1989) was the first to establish the notion of real earnings management (REM). Olotu et al. (2019) defined actual earnings management as a method of manipulating reported results by timing financing or investment choices. They said further that real earnings management entailed real-world company actions with a direct impact on operating cash flows. Ewert and Wagenhofer (2005) defined real earnings management as changes in the structure of real business activities with the goal of changing earnings. Real earnings management, according to Roychowdhury (2006), is a departure from typical operating practices motivated by managers' desire to deceive some stakeholders into believing that certain financial reporting targets have been met in the course of normal operations.

It is worthy to note that real earnings management affects earnings through mechanisms of scheduling actual business activity decisions such as operating, investing, or financing operations in accordance with pre-determined earnings targets (Olotu et al., 2019). These choices have a direct impact on operational cash flows and, as a result, Chief

Executive Officers influence real operating decisions to serve their own interests, which does not result in a genuine and reliable depiction of the organization's economic success. According to Sun and Ian (2014), real earnings management has a detrimental impact on company value. Investors are hesitant to speculate on the company since it is difficult to differentiate between earnings management and real activities. This is because earning management has a negative impact on future cash flows that is real earnings management can lower a company's value (Roychowdhury, 2006).

Market Value

Firm value is an illustration of the value of the stock price as a result of the company's success in running a business (Dzahabiyya et al., 2020). The implementation of corporate governance in the company is expected to increase and maximize the value of the company. The basic principles that exist during the implementation of corporate governance in companies are expected to increase the confidence of creditors and investors, both domestic and foreign.

The equity value creation submitted that the book value of firms can be viewed in terms of net deferred tax, assets and liabilities. It can also be viewed in term of net interest payable.

The market value, according to Muhammed and Isah, (2017) is viewed as the non-operating assets of the firms such as excess cash, financial fixed assets, and non-consolidated investments to value of operation. The Heineken's value creation constitutes four elements, which

includes; financial asset, sale of investment, non-consolidated investments of equity holding in the firms (associated and joint venture) and excess cash. Furthermore, value can be viewed as a dimension of measurement in a market economy, showing that people invest with the expectation that after selling the goods or products, the value of their investment will grow more than the cost price which in turn compensates them for the risk they took (Muhammed & Isah, 2017). On the other hand, when value is measured in the long term, it treats current and former employees better, gives customers more satisfaction and creates more employment. To this end, Olaoye and Adewumi (2018) stated that the principle of value creation lies in the domain of individual firms; as firms invest capital generated from the Investors, value is created through future cash flows from the investments. This is clearly seen when return generated by the companies exceed the cost of capital (the rate investors are paid for the use of their capital). The faster companies can increase their revenues and deploy more capital to increase rates of return and in turn creates more value. This is also referred to as conservatism which is the combination of growth and return on invested capital relative to its cost drive value.

Theoretical Framework

This study, adopts the resource-based theory and positive accounting theory as the theoretical framework. The resource-based theory is adopted because it takes cognizance of the need to develop and use internal resources

(intellectual capital) through board decisions, which could be facilitated by equity in gender representation (Hsu *et al.*, 2018; Ahmad & Sallau, 2018). The board size that incorporates gender diversity is the central organ of an organization that performs strategic decision, controlled and monitored firm for short and long run growth and survival (Agyei-Mensah, 2018; Moreno-Gomez et al., 2017). Hence, earnings resource-based theory gives credence to the role of female board members in shaping the firm strategic decision. The study also anchored on positive accounting theory because it is based on an underlying economic assumption called the “rational economic person” assumption, which assumes that all individuals act in their own self-interest and are rational wealth maximisers. According to Scott (2003), positive accounting theory attempts to make good predictions for real world and practical accounting events. Since, positive accounting provides justifications for why managers engage in earnings management, this study has found it relevant in explaining the link between firm value and earnings management. In line with the theory, managers engage in earnings management in order to protect their reputations which have implication on the market value of the firms.

Empirical Review

Huang et al. (2021) examined the impact of earnings management and board characteristics on firm efficiency, the researchers used data envelopment analysis (DEA) and the Tobin q regression model from 2009 to 2017. 396

Taiwanese electronics and biotechnology enterprises were sampled. The authors discovered that earnings management had a minor impact on firm efficiency, with inconsistent results on the effects of earnings management and board characteristics.

Wilson (2021) investigated whether real earnings management (REM) has an impact on the value-relevance of cash flows from operations (CFO). Higher degrees of real earnings management were linked to lower CFO value-relevance, according to the findings. This research contributes to a better understanding of how real earnings management affects CFO valuation utility and identifies a specific situation in which CFO information quality deteriorates.

By integrating corporate governance as moderating variable, Afrizal et al. (2021) investigated the influence of earnings management on company value. The research looks at the impact of earnings management on firm value as well as the function of corporate governance in reducing earnings management practices and increasing firm value. Previous research had discovered empirical evidence of a beneficial association between earnings management and business value. According to the findings, earnings management methods had a favourable impact on company value, which was mitigated by corporate governance.

E1 Deeb (2019) analysed integrated reporting on firm value and performance of firms listed in EGX30 index in the Egyptian stock exchange market between 2012 and 2017. The data for the

study were obtained from the annual reports of the sampled companies and the data collected were analysed using descriptive analysis, Pearson correlation and regression analysis. The findings of the study revealed that integrated reporting index positively affects firm performance and value and the leverage level of the companies.

Susanto (2017) investigated the impact of accrual and real earnings management on the value of a company. The study was based on a sample size of 162 non-financial companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange from 2012 to 2015, and the data was analysed using the multiple regression approach. The study's empirical findings revealed that real profits management had a negative and significant impact on firm value. Investors are hesitant to speculate on the company since it is difficult to distinguish earnings management from real activities.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed “*ex-post facto*” research design to achieve the objectives of the study. The population of this study consisted of 51 listed manufacturing firms. Purposive sampling method was employed having eliminated manufacturing companies that were not listed as at 2014 and not fully in operation for the period under study. Hence, the sample size for the study is 38. Secondary data was collected from published financial report and accounts of selected 38 listed manufacturing firms from 2011 to 2021. Data collected were analysed using

descriptive static pane1 regression technique in addition with relevant diagnostic tests

Mode1 Specification

This model adapted Sarun, (2016), model to achieve the objective as follow:

$TOBQ = f(REM, LeV, PROF, FIS,)$

$$TOBQ_{it} = \lambda_0 + \lambda_1 REM_{it} + \lambda_2 LEV_{it} + \lambda_3 PROF_{it} + \lambda_4 FSI_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad 3.2$$

Where;

λ_0 , intercepts,

$\lambda_1 - \lambda_5$ are estimated coefficients of mode1

ToBQ = Tobins q

SP= Share price

REM= Real earnings management Proxy by Prod

leV = leverage

FIS= Firm size

PRoF= Profitability (RoA)

ε_{it} = Error terms

Note the subscription index “it”

i = firm, t = time,

Measurement of Variables

Independent Variable.

Real activity-based earnings management (REM): Roychowdhury (2006), Zhang (2006) and Gunny (2005) considered three measures of the degree of real earnings management: They are the abnormal levels of the cash flow from operating activities abnormal levels, discretionary expenses and costs of production. In this study, cost of production measure was used for measuring the degree of real earnings management and the following mode1 was to estimate the level of production costs:

$$Prod_{it} / TA_{it-1} = \alpha_0 + \alpha \left(\frac{1}{TA_{it-1}} \right) \alpha_0 + \beta_1 \left(\frac{S_{it}}{TA_{it-1}} \right) + \beta_2 \left(\frac{\Delta S_{it}}{TA_{it-1}} \right) + \beta_3 \left(\frac{\Delta S_{it-1}}{TA_{it-1}} \right) + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

Where:

$Prod_{it}$ = total production costs for firm i, period t,

TA_{it-1} = total assets at the end for firm i, period t-1

***Akosile Akindele Iyiola, Akinkunmi Maruf Akinsola and Olowolaju Philip Segun**

S_{it} = sales revenue for firm i , period t

ΔS_{it} = change in for firm i , period t

ΔS_{it-1} = lagged change in sales revenue for firm i , period $t-1$

Table 1: Measurement of Variables

Variables	Type of Variable	Variable labels	Measurement	Supporting scholar	Expected sign
Market Value					
Tobin q Share price	Dependent	ToBQ	<u>market value of equity + book value of debt</u> Total assets	Sarun, 2016;	
Real Earnings Management	Independent	REM	Total production costs (TPC)	Abata & Migoro, 2016;	±
Leverage	Contro1	Lev	Total Debt/ Total assets	Hasan et al,2022; Gbadebo (2021)	±
Firm size	Contro1	FIS	Natural log of total assets	Hasan et al,2022; Ilaboya & lodiker o (2017)	+
Profitability (Return on Assets)	Contro1	ROA	Profit after tax as ratio of Total assets	Hasan et al,2022;	+

Source: Author's Compilation (2023)

***Akosile Akindele Iyiola, Akinkunmi Maruf Akinsola and Olowolaju Philip Segun**

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of the Variables

	ToBQ	REMD	PRoF	FSI	LeVT
Mean	1.811	0.027	4.0253	7.184	2.4723
Median	1.157	0.016	4.1756	7.127	1.2895
Maximum	11.298	0.381	53.959	9.240	20.90
Minimum	0.124	0.000	-179.91	5.092	-31.0
Std. Dev.	1.622	0.039	15.791	0.915	16.43
Skewness	2.439	4.464	-4.6223	-0.0277	-19.061
Kurtosis	9.949	31.777	52.904	2.2305	368
Jar-Bera	1138.7	14336.	40678	9.398	213267
Probability	0.000	0.000	0.0000	0.0091	0.0000
Sum	686.4	10.570	1525.6	2722.9	-2453
Sum Sq.	995.47	0.583	94259.	317.07	985069
Obs	418	418	418	418	418

Source: Author’s Computation, 2025

The descriptive statistics of the variables used in the study are contained in Table 2. From the results, the average Tobin Q, which is the baseline measure of market value, is 1.811 while its corresponding standard deviation of 1.622 suggests no wide variation in the Tobin Q of the sampled listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The estimated average real earnings management is found to be 0.027 with standard

deviation of 0.039. For the control variables, the estimated average firm size of the study is 7.184 with a corresponding standard deviation of 0.915 which suggests no wide variation in the size of the listed Nigerian manufacturing firms. By implication, Nigeria listed manufacturing firms are nearly equal in size. Also, the estimated average profitability represented by return on asset of the sampled firms is found to be 4.025

***Akosile Akindele Iyiola, Akinkunmi Maruf Akinsola and Olowolaju Philip Segun**

with a minimum and maximum of -179.91 and 53.959 respectively, while the corresponding standard deviation of 15.791 obtained revealed that there is very high variation in the RoA of Nigerian listed manufacturing firms. Equally, the average financial leverage of the sampled manufacturing firms is 2.47 with a standard deviation of 16.43 which suggest wide variation the financial leverage of Nigerian manufacturing firms. The study equally conducted a Jacque

Bera normality test to check for the violation of normality assumptions. In each of all the variables used in the study, the estimated p-value of Jacque Bera is less than 0.05 which suggest that the null hypothesis that each of those variables are normally distributed is rejected at 5%. By implication, the outcome of Jacque Bera test suggests that each of the variables are not normally distributed.

Correlation Results

Table 3: Estimated Correlation Coefficient among the Variables

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
(1) ToBQ	1.000				
(2) REMD	-0.165	1.000			
(3) PRoF	0.287	-0.110	1.000		
(4) FSI	0.106	0.203	0.297	1.000	
(5) leVT	0.004	0.104	0.245	0.127	1.000

Source: Author’s Computation, 2025

The results obtained from correlation analysis of the variables are presented in Table 3. The results in the table revealed that Tobin Q which proxy market value are positively related as shown by the estimated correlation coefficient of 0.567. The estimated correlation coefficient of --0.165 revealed that real earnings management is negatively associated with Tobin Q of the sample manufacturing firms. Equally, the estimated correlation coefficient of 0.287 and in the table revealed that profitability is positively related

with Tobin Q respectively. The respective estimated correlation coefficient of 0.106 in the obtained results indicates that firm size is positively associated with Tobin Q. Also, the firms financial leverage is positively associated with Tobin Q of the sampled firms given the respective correlation coefficient of 0.004. As regards the association among the explanatory variables, the results presented in Table 4.2 reveal that the explanatory variables are not highly related as the highest estimated

***Akosile Akindele Iyiola, Akinkunmi Maruf Akinsola and Olowolaju Philip Segun**

correlation coefficient. Hence, the relatively lower correlation among the explanatory variables of the study implies that

multicollinearity problem is not likely to occur.

Diagnostic Results

Table 4: Estimated Variance Inflation Factor for Model One

	VIF	1/VIF
PRoF	1.154	.867
FSI	1.136	.88
LeVT	1.073	.932
REMD	1.051	.951
Mean VIF	1.104	.

Source: Author’s Computation, 2025

The results of the variance inflation factors presented in Table 4 revealed that profitability records the highest VIF of 1.154 followed closely by firm size with VIF of 1.136, financial leverage with VIF of 1.073 and real earnings management

with VIF of 1.051. Since the highest VIF is less than the threshold of 10, the model used in achieving objective 1 of the study is free of multicollinearity problem.

Table 5: Diagnostic Test Results for Heteroskedasticity and Serial Correlation

Market Value Proxies	Test Type	Statistics	P Value	Remarks
Tobin Q	Breusch-pagan heteroscedasticity Test	1.19	0.2763	No Heteroscedasticity
	Wooldridge Test for first order serial correlation	109.439	0.000	Presence of first order serial correlation

Source: Author’s Computation, 2025

The results of the Breusch-Pagan test for heteroscedasticity presented in Table 5 revealed an estimated Chi square of 1.19 with p - value of 0.276 when market value is measured with Tobin Q. This implies that the null hypotheses of no heteroscedasticity is not rejected at 5 per cent level when market value is measured with Tobin Q. The results of the Wooldridge test for

autocorrelation are equally presented in Table 5 with F value of 109.439 and p - value of 0.000 when market value is measured with Tobin Q, implying that the null hypothesis of no serial correlation is rejected at 5% level of significance. Hence, the results of the Wooldridge test establish the existence of serial correlation for model of the study.

***Akosile Akindele Iyiola, Akinkunmi Maruf Akinsola and Olowolaju Philip Segun**

Regression Results

Table 6: Estimated Pane1 Regression Results (Dep = ToBQ)

VARIABLES	(1) POls	(2) Fixed Effect	(3) Random Effect
REMD ₁	-5.834*** (-3.395)	-2.799** (-2.411)	-3.773*** (-2.974)
PrOF	0.0299 (1.610)	0.00383 (0.337)	0.00763 (0.529)
FSI	0.00156 (0.0147)	-1.007** (-2.354)	-0.386** (-2.026)
LeVT	-0.000832** (-2.024)	0.000864*** (3.829)	0.000645** (2.374)
Constant	1.837** (2.385)	9.115*** (2.969)	4.659*** (3.331)
Observations	418	418	418
R-squared	0.306	0.301	0.321
Number of PID	38	38	38
Chow F		20.30	
Chow P Val		0.000	
Hausman Chi		36.06	
Hausman P val		0.000	

Robust t-statistics in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Source: Author's Computation 2025

The results in table 6 are obtained from the alternative pane1 regression techniques including the pooled ols, fixed effect and random

effect. The results obtained using pooled ols are presented in column 1 while the results obtained using fixed effect and random effect are

***Akosile Akindele Iyiola, Akinkunmi Maruf Akinsola and Olowolaju Philip Segun**

contained in column 2 and 3. The results of the specification tests for mode1 of the study are presented in the lower part of the table. The specification tests conducted include the Chow F-test for firm effect and the Hausman test for the non-systematic differences in the coefficient. From the results, F-value of 20.30 with associated p - value of 0.000 indicates that the null hypothesis has no effect and it is rejected suggesting that the use of Pooled ols will not bring consistent result. Equally, the results of the Hausman test with an estimated chi-square value of 36.06 and p - value of 0.000 rejects the null hypothesis of non-systematic differences in the coefficient implying that fixed effect pane1 regression performs better than the random effect pane1 regression mode1. Hence, the results of mode1 for Tobin Q which is the measure for market value is based on the results of fixed pane1 regression in column 2 of Table 6.

The results in column 2 obtained from fixed effect pane1 regression revealed that real earnings management exerts negative influence ($\beta=-2.799$) on Tobin Q which is significant at 5% level ($t=-2.411$; $p<0.05$). This implies that real earnings management has significant negative influence on the market value of Nigerian manufacturing firms represented by Tobin Q. With regards to the control variables, results of the fixed effect pane1 regression in column 2 of the table indicate that firm size has negative impact on market value of manufacturing firms in Nigeria ($\beta=-1.007$) and became insignificant at 5 per cent level of significance ($t=-2.354$;

$p<0.05$) on the Tobin Q. This indicated that firm size may lead to a reduction in market value of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Also, the results of the fixed effect pane1 regression in the table revealed that profitability exerts positive influence on firm value ($\beta=0.0038$) insignificant influence ($t=0.337$; $p>0.05$) on Tobin Q of the sampled manufacturing firms in Nigeria. This indicated that profitability enhances the market value. In addition, the results of the fixed effect pane1 regression in Table 6 further revealed that financial leverage with estimated coefficient of 0.00086 and corresponding t value of 3.829 had positive impact which is significant at 5 per cent level of significance ($t=3.829$; $p<0.05$) on the Tobin Q of the sampled Nigerian manufacturing firms. According to the results, the null hypothesis that real earnings management does not affect the market value of the firms measured with Tobin Q is rejected at 5 per cent level of significance while the corresponding null hypothesis that real earnings management does not affect the market value measured with market share price is not rejected.

Discussion of Findings

In respect of the first objective of the study, the results revealed a negative impact of real earnings management on the market value of Nigerian manufacturing firms measured with Tobin Q and market share price. The negative impact suggests that engaging in real earnings management strategies adversely affects the perceived credibility and reliability of financial statements. Investors and the market, in general,

***Akosile Akindele Iyiola, Akinkunmi Maruf Akinsola and Olowolaju Philip Segun**

are likely to view such practices as attempts to manipulate earnings for short-term gains, eroding trust in the financial information provided by the firm. The findings imply that the market penalizes firms practicing real earnings management, indicating a concern among investors about the long-term sustainability and value of these companies. Investors may interpret such manipulative practices as a sign that the reported financial performance does not accurately reflect the underlying economic realities of the firm. Negative market reactions could also be attributed to increased information asymmetry. Real earnings management may make it challenging for investors to accurately assess the true financial health and performance of the company, leading to increased uncertainty and a subsequent decrease in market value. The results obtained here aligns with the submission of Afrizal et al. (2021) that real earnings management had negative influence on the market value, and E1 Deeb (2019) who reported that integrated reporting increases the value of Egyptian firms. The findings here equally agreed with that of Susanto (2017) who reported negative and significant impact of real earnings management on the market value of the firm. The findings here however fail to agree with the findings of Nurkumalasari et al. (2019) in a study of Asian firms which reported that integrated reporting disclosure does not affect the firm value.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concluded that real earnings management are detrimental to the market value of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study found negative and significant impact of real earnings management on the proxies of market value. Based on this study, it is thus recommended that management of Nigerian manufacturing firms should put measures in place to limit the practice of real earnings management. The study has contributed to the debate on the implication on real earnings management which firms are now shifting to. The study demonstrated that engaging in real earnings management by Nigerian manufacturing firms is opportunistic as it is at the expense of the company's stockholders.

REFERENCES

- Abata, M.A., & Migiro, S. O. (2016). Corporate governance and management of earnings: Empirical evidence from selected Nigerian-listed companies. *Investment Management and Financial Innovations*, 13(2-1), 189-205.
- Abbas, A., & Ayub, U. (2019). Role of earnings management in determining firm value: An emerging economy perspective. *International Journal of Advanced and Applied Sciences*, 6(6), 103-116
- Abdullahi, B.A., Norfadzilah, R., Umar, A.M., & Ademola, 1.S. (2020). The financial determinants of earnings management and the profitability of listed companies in

***Akosile Akindede Iyiola, Akinkunmi Maruf Akinsola and Olowolaju Philip Segun**

- Nigeria, *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(9), 32-38.
- Akuntansi Dan Keuangan Dewantara, 4(1), 46–55.
- Abdullah, S.N., & Mohammed, N. (2004). Accrual management and the independence of the board of directors and audit committees. *IIUM Journal of Economics and Management*, 12(1), 49 – 80
- El Deeb, H. (2019). Integrated reporting on firm value and performance of firms listed in EGX30 index in the Egyptian stock exchange market. *International Journal of Managerial Studies and Research (IJMSR)*, 6 (10), 55-69.
- Afrizal. J, Gamayuni, R.R., & Syaipudin, U. (2021) Effect of earnings management on firm value with corporate governance as a moderating variable. *International Journal for Innovation Education and Research*, 9(02), 262-268
- Ewert, R., & Wagenhofer, A. (2005). Economic effects of tightening accounting standards to restrict earnings management. *The Accounting Review*, 80(4), 1101–1124.
- Ahmad H. S., & Sallau, M. M. (2018). Corporate governance and the market value of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Accounting and Taxation Review*, 2, 28-42.
- Gulzar, M.A. & Wang, Z. (2011). Corporate governance characteristics and earnings management; empirical evidence from Chinese listed firms, *International Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 1(1), 133-151
- Agyei-Mensah, B. (2018). Impact of corporate governance attributes and financial reporting lag on corporate financial performance. *African Journal of Economic and Management Studies*, 9(3)97-110.
- Gunny, K. (2005). What are the consequences of real earnings management? . Working paper. University of Colorado. 46.
- Dzahabiyya, J., Jhoansyah, D., & Danial, R. D. M. (2020). Analisis Firm value dengan Mode1 Rasio Tobin's Q. *JAD: Jurnal Riset*
- Gunny, K. (2010). The relation between earnings management using real activities manipulation and future performance: evidence from meeting earnings benchmarks. *Contemporary Accounting Research* 27(3), 855-888.

- Hepworth, S.R. (1953). Periodic income smoothing. *The Accounting Review*, 28(1), 32-39.
- Hsu, C., lai, W., & Yen, S. (2018). Boardroom diversity and operating performance: the moderating effect of strategic change. *Emerging Markets Finance and Trade*, 1-28
- Huang, H.-1., liang, 1.-W., Chang, H.-Y., & Hsu, H.-Y. (2021). The influence of earnings management and board characteristics on company efficiency. *Sustainability*, 13, 1-17.
- Liu, J. 1., & Tsai, C.C (2015). Board member characteristics and ownership structure impacts on real earning management: Evidence From Taiwan. *Accounting and Finance Research*, 4(4), 84-96.
- McNichols, M.F. (2000). Research design issues in earnings management studies. *Journal of Accounting and Public policy*, 19(4-5), 313-345. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0278-4254\(00\)00018-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0278-4254(00)00018-1)
- Moreno-Gomez, J., lafuenta, E., & Vaillant, Y. (2017). Gender diversity in the board, women leadership and business performance Gender in Management: *An International Journal*, doi:10.108/GM-05-2017-0058
- Muhammad, 1., & Isah, A. I. (2017). Determinants of shareholders' value creation of listed building materials firms in Nigeria. *ATBU Journal of Science, Technology and Education*, 5(2), 119-130.
- Nwaobia, A.N., Kwarbai, J.D., & Fregene, O.O. (2019), Earnings management and corporate survival of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria, *International Journal of Development and Sustainability*, 8(2), 97-115.
- Nurkumalasari, I.S., Restuningdish, N. & Sidharta, E.A. (2019). Integrated reporting disclosure and its impact on firm value: Evidence in Asia, *International Journal of Business, Economics & law*, 18(5), 99 – 108
- Okafor, T.G., & Ezeagba, C.E. (2018). Effect of earnings management on performance of corporate organization in Nigeria, *International Journal of Business Management and Economic Review*, 1(03), 74-87.
- Olaoye, F. & Adewumi, A., (2018). Corporate governance and earning management of deposit money banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research* 9, 7, 2229-5518
- Olotu, E., Salawu, R.O., Adegbe, F.F., &

***Akosile Akindele Iyiola, Akinkunmi Maruf Akinsola and Olowolaju Philip Segun**

- Akinwunmi, A.J (2019). Earnings management and performance of Nigerian quoted manufacturing companies: the Balanced Scorecard Approach. *International Journal of Advanced Studies in Business Strategies and Management* 7, (I) 76-98.
- Remenaric, B., Kenfelja, I., & Mijoc, I. (2018). Creative accounting: motives, techniques and possibilities of prevention, *Ekonomski Vjesnik, Econviews*, 193-199.
- Roychowdhury, S. (2006). “Earnings management through real activities manipulation”, *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 42(3), 335-370.
- Subramanyam, K.R. (2014). The pricing of discretionary accruals. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 22(1-3),249-281. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-4101\(96\)00434-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-4101(96)00434-X)
- Salome,I.O, Akani, F.N.,& Ironkwe, U. I. (2021).Effect of accrual-based earnings management on the financial performance of manufacturing companies in Nigeria. *European Scholar Journal (ESJ)*, 2 (7) 77-84.
- Sanyaolu , W.A.,& Job-Olatunji, K.A. (2017). Effect of earnings management on shareholders wealth maximization: evidence from Nigerian listed Firms. *International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research*, 6(4), 67-74
- Sarun, A. (2016). Corporate governance, earnings quality and firm value: Evidence from Malaysia Ph.D Thesis submitted to Victoria Institute for Strategic Economic Studies (VISES) *College of Business Victoria University*.
- Schipper, K. (1989). Commentary on earnings management, *Accounting Horizons*, (4): 91–102.
- Scott, W. R. (2012). Financial accounting theory, edisi 6. Pearson Prentice Hall. USA.
- Scott, W. (2003). Financial accounting theory, (3rd ed.), Toronto: Pearson Education Inc.
- Securities Exchange Commission (SEC), (2011), Code of Best Practices on Corporate Governance of Nigeria
- SusantoY. K (2017) Accrual earnings management, real earnings management, firm value. *International Journal of Business, Economics and law*, 14, (1), 1-6
- Sun, J., & Lan.G. (2014). Independent audit committee characteristics and real

***Akosile Akindele Iyiola, Akinkunmi Maruf Akinsola and Olowolaju Philip Segun**

- earnings management. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 29(2), 153-172.
- Sunardi, M. S. (2018). The effect of earnings management on firm value before and when IFRS implementation, Dimodation life cycle company. *Journal of Business and Economics*. 9(3),275-285
- Tolulope, I., Uwuigbe, U., Uwuigbe,O.R., Emmanue1, O., Oriabie, S., & Asiriuwa, O.(2018). The effect of corporate governance attributes on earnings management: A Study of listed Companies in Nigeria. *Academy of Strategic Management Journal* 17(6) ,1-11
- Ubesie, M. C, Nwankwo, B.G.O., & Ogbogu, N.P.E. (2020). Appraisal of the impact of earnings management on financial performance of consumer goods firms in Nigeria. *Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 8(1): 34-47. 22.
- Umoren, A., Ikpantan, I., & Ededeh, D. (2018). Earnings management and financial performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria, *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 9(22), 94-100
- Umobong, A., & Akani, D. (2015). IFRS Adoption and Accounting Quality of Quoted Manufacturing Firms in Nigeria: A cross-sectional study of brewery and cement manufacturing firms. *International Journal of Business and Management Review*, 3(6), 61-77.
- Uwuigbe, O. R. (2011). Corporate governance and financial performance of banks: A study of listed banks in Nigerisa (Ph.D. Thesis). Covenant University, ota, Nigeria
- Wilson, G. (2015). The effect of real earnings management on the information content of earnings. *Journal of Finance and Accountancy*, 19, 1.
- Zhang J (2006). The contracting benefits of accounting conservatism to lenders and borrowers. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 45(1): 27-54. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jacceco.2007.06.002>